

PHILOSOPHICAL ORIENTATION AND PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICES OF PRE-SERVICE ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS: A PROPOSED PRIMER

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers, with a focus on how their beliefs influenced the teaching of the five macro skills: listening, speaking, reading, writing, and viewing. Conducted at the CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc. in Sariaya, Quezon, the research utilized a quantitative correlational design to examine the relationship between educational philosophies and classroom strategies. Data were collected using a structured, close-ended survey questionnaire administered to the entire population of pre-service English language teachers at the institution. The instrument measured respondents' philosophical orientations drawing from essentialism, behaviorism, linguistic philosophy, and other educational perspectives as well as their teaching practices across macro skills. Statistical analyses, including weighted arithmetic mean and Pearson correlation coefficient, were employed to interpret the data. Findings revealed that participants strongly adhered to essentialism, behaviorism, and linguistic philosophy, with progressivism and existentialism moderately embraced. Their pedagogical practices were also highly favorable, particularly in writing and viewing, reflecting a blend of structured instruction and learner-centered engagement. Significant correlations were found between essentialism and all macro skill areas, especially writing, which was influenced by multiple philosophical orientations. However, some orientations like constructivism showed limited alignment with actual teaching practices. The study concluded that philosophical beliefs significantly impacted instructional choices, and

recommended the development of a primer that integrated these orientations into practical teaching strategies. This primer aimed to support pre-service teachers in aligning their educational philosophies with effective, reflective, and responsive English language instruction.

Keywords: *instructional alignment, pedagogical practices, philosophical orientation, pre-service language teachers, teacher education*

INTRODUCTION

Teacher education plays a vital role in shaping the effectiveness of future educators, particularly in the field of English language teaching. One of the significant challenges in this domain is the alignment between philosophical orientations and practical teaching approaches. Many pre-service teachers enter the profession with varying educational philosophies that influence their instructional strategies, yet there remains a gap in understanding how these orientations affect their ability to teach macro skills—listening, speaking, reading, writing, and viewing. This misalignment may lead to ineffective language instruction, thereby impacting students' proficiency and overall language development. As a result, addressing the interplay between philosophical beliefs and teaching practices is crucial in enhancing teacher training programs and ensuring quality English language education.

Scholars have explored various teaching philosophies and their implications for language instruction. Perennialism, for instance, emphasizes timeless knowledge and classical literature, advocating for structured and teacher-centered instruction (Hutchins, 1953). Essentialism focuses on a core curriculum that develops fundamental skills, ensuring mastery of language components through systematic instruction (Bagley, 1938). Progressivism, championed by Dewey (1938), highlights experiential learning and student-centered approaches, encouraging active engagement in language acquisition. Existentialism, on the other hand, prioritizes individual choice and personal meaning in learning, fostering autonomy in language development (Sartre, 1943). Reconstructionism, as proposed by Brameld (1950), advocates for education as a means of social change, integrating real-world issues into language instruction to develop critical thinking and societal awareness. These philosophical perspectives provided theoretical foundations that influence the teaching methodologies of pre-service English language teachers. However, despite the growing body of literature on teaching philosophies and language instruction, there remains a need to explore how these orientations specifically affect the teaching of macro skills among pre-service teachers.

The lack of explicit integration of philosophical orientations in teacher education programs raises concerns about the effectiveness of pedagogical training. Research indicates that many pre-service teachers struggle to translate their theoretical knowledge into classroom practice, leading to inconsistencies in language instruction (Darling-Hammond, 2006). Furthermore, according to UNESCO (2021), only 44% of teachers in developing countries receive adequate training in language pedagogy, highlighting the

need for more structured teacher education programs. Legal frameworks such as the Education Act and national teacher competency standards emphasize the importance of well-rounded teacher preparation. However, statistical data suggest that a significant proportion of teachers feel underprepared to teach English macro skills effectively, calling for a more robust approach to integrating philosophical orientations into teacher training.

Thus, this study aims to investigate the philosophical orientations of pre-service English language teachers and examined how these orientations influence their teaching practices concerning the macro skills of language learning. By identifying these orientations and their practical implications, this research seeks to provide a comprehensive primer that can guide teacher educators, policymakers, and curriculum developers in enhancing pre-service teacher training programs. Understanding this relationship could contribute to improving instructional effectiveness, thereby addressing industry challenges related to teacher preparedness and language education quality. Ultimately, the study aspires to support the development of more competent English language teachers, fostering better student outcomes and advancing language education as a whole.

Research Questions

The objective of this study was to examine the relationship between the pre-service English language teachers' philosophical orientation and pedagogical practices.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions.

1. What are the philosophical orientations of Pre-service ELTs in terms of:
 - 1.1. Progressivism;
 - 1.2. Perennialism;
 - 1.3. Existentialism;
 - 1.4. Behaviorism;
 - 1.5. Essentialism;
 - 1.6. Constructivism; and
 - 1.7. Linguistic Philosophy?
2. What are the pedagogical practices of Pre-Service ELTs and components as to:
 - 2.1. Listening;
 - 2.2. Speaking;
 - 2.3. Reading;
 - 2.4. Writing;
 - 2.5. Viewing; and
 - 2.6. General Teaching Practices?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the pre-service ELTs' philosophical orientation and pedagogical practices?
4. What primer can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researchers employed a quantitative research approach. Quantitative research involved the collection and analysis of numerical data and was commonly used to identify patterns, relationships, and averages (Bhandari, 2023). This approach was appropriate for the study as it allowed for the systematic measurement and analysis of the relationship between the philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers. By using numerical data, the researchers identified the correlation and potential associations between these two key variables. A notable advantage of the quantitative method was the objectivity and reliability of the data collected. The use of standardized instruments and statistical analysis minimized researcher bias and ensured that the findings were grounded in empirical evidence (Aithor, 2024).

A correlational research design was used in this study. This non-experimental method enabled the researchers to examine the degree and nature of the statistical relationship between two variables without manipulating them (Bhandari, 2023). In this context, the correlational design helped determine whether, and to what extent, the philosophical orientations of pre-service English language teachers were related to their pedagogical practices.

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communication, Inc., located in Sariaya, Quezon. The institution offered a Teacher Education Program that caters to a diverse group of pre-service teachers, particularly those specializing in English language instruction. These pre-service teachers came from various socio-economic and linguistic backgrounds, providing a rich context for exploring their philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices. The setting was ideal for examining how these future educators developed their teaching philosophies and classroom strategies as they prepared for professional practice.

In line with this, the chosen locale allowed for an in-depth investigation of how pre-service teachers' philosophical orientations influenced their pedagogical decisions particularly in relation to English language instruction. Ryan (2008) emphasized that most pre-service teachers entered teacher education programs with well-formed philosophical beliefs, primarily rooted in progressivism, which played a significant role in shaping their instructional approaches. Exploring these orientations within the context of a linguistically and culturally diverse institution provided an opportunity to identify how such beliefs inform strategies for improving language skills. This localized focus contributed valuable insights toward the development of a practical and philosophically informed teaching primer.

Research Population and Sample

This study involved all pre-service English language teachers who were enrolled in the Teacher Education Program at the CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communication, Inc., located in Sariaya, Quezon. Since the total number of these students was small and manageable, the researchers chose to include the whole population instead of selecting only a portion or sample.

Using the entire population ensured that the data collected reflected the true range of philosophical orientations and teaching practices of all the pre-service teachers in the institution. It also helped avoid selection bias, which could happen when only a few individuals were chosen, possibly leaving out important perspectives or experiences. Including everyone increased the accuracy and reliability of the findings. By doing so, the researchers better understood how different teaching beliefs connected to classroom practices. This approach led to more meaningful conclusions and a clearer basis for creating the proposed primer.

Research Instrument

The researchers utilized a close-ended survey questionnaire to gather data relevant to the philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers. According to Bhandari (2023), close-ended questionnaires consisted of standardized questions that ensured uniformity in the data collection process, enabling reliable and consistent results across respondents. The instrument was divided into three main sections.

The first part collected the demographic profile of the respondents, including age, sex, and grade level(s) taught during their practice teaching, which helped in understanding the background diversity of the participants. The second part was the Philosophical Orientation Assessment, adapted from The Teaching Profession 3rd Edition developed by Bilbao et al. (2015), which consisted of 25 statements. The researchers modified it by adding 3 more statements to make it relevant for the study. The instrument was composed of 28 statements that reflected various educational philosophies. Respondents indicated their level of agreement using a 4-point Likert scale: Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. These items were designed to reveal the underlying beliefs and values that guided the respondents' perspectives on teaching and learning.

Finally, Teaching Practices of the Macro Skills, developed by the researchers, evaluated the pedagogical practices of pre-service teachers across the five macro skills of language learning—Listening, Speaking, Reading, Writing, and Viewing—as well as their general teaching practices. Each macro skill category consisted of five items, also rated on a 4-point Likert scale. This section aimed to assess how philosophical orientations were reflected in classroom teaching strategies. The questionnaires underwent content validation by field experts to ensure the relevance, clarity, and appropriateness of each item. The structured nature of the instrument, combined with

statistical analysis, allowed the researchers to explore the relationship between philosophical orientation and pedagogical practices in a systematic and objective manner.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before the distribution of questionnaires, the researchers asked for permission from the necessary individuals at the CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc. to allow them to conduct the study in the school. The distribution and answering of questionnaires were done at the most convenient time.

The research instruments underwent face and content validity by their research adviser and an internal and external validator to comply with their needed purpose in data collection and for proper validation before distribution to the respondents.

The distribution of questionnaires was followed by proper orientation about the instructions of the questionnaires and the main objective of the study. Through this, the answers on each questionnaire were evaluated and calculated by the researchers. The collected data were studied and carefully managed through statistical procedures. Under the Data Privacy Act of 2012, the information obtained regarding the respondents of the study remained confidential to protect their rights.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In analyzing the philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices of the respondents, the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) was used for both variables. The WAM was calculated by multiplying each response by its corresponding weight, summing all the weighted scores, and then dividing by the total number of responses. This method helped determine the overall average for each item or set of items in the questionnaire. The weighted mean allowed the researchers to identify which philosophical beliefs and teaching practices were most and least emphasized among the pre-service English language teachers. By comparing the WAM results of the two variables, the researchers explored possible patterns or relationships between the respondents' educational philosophies and their teaching approaches.

Formula:

$$WAM = (\Sigma x) \div n$$

The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to compare the gathered data as it proved appropriate for the study. According to Turney (2024), the Pearson correlation coefficient was a descriptive statistic, meaning that it summarized the characteristics of a dataset. Specifically, it described the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables. Importantly, it was crucial to remember that correlation did not imply causation. While a strong correlation might have suggested a causal relationship between two variables, it did not necessarily prove it. Furthermore, McClenaghan (2024) stated that Pearson's correlation helped researchers understand

the relationship between two quantitative variables when the relationship between them was assumed to take a linear pattern. This meant that Pearson's r was used to test whether the observed correlation between two variables was statistically significant, suggesting that it was unlikely to have occurred by chance alone. The Pearson correlation coefficient told how closely the two variables—philosophical orientation and pedagogical practices—changed together in a linear fashion, and whether they increased or decreased together (positive correlation), or whether one variable increased as the other decreased (negative correlation).

Formula:

$$r = \frac{[n\Sigma xy - (\Sigma x)(\Sigma y)]}{\sqrt{[n\Sigma x^2 - (\Sigma x)^2][n\Sigma y^2 - (\Sigma y)^2]}}$$

n = number of pairs of weighted average mean

Σxy = sum of the paired weighted average mean

Σx = sum of philosophical orientation WAM

Σy = sum of pedagogical practices WAM

Σx^2 = sum of squared philosophical orientation WAM

Σy^2 = sum of squared pedagogical practices WAM

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Part I. Philosophical Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

Table 1

Progressivist Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
3	I encourage students to interact with each other to build social virtues like cooperation and respect.	3.67	Strongly Agree
4	I help students expand knowledge by applying previous experiences to solve new problems.	3.44	Strongly Agree
1	I believe there is no substitute for concrete experience in learning.	3.06	Agree
2	I believe students should not be forced to learn subjects that do not interest them.	2.71	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.22	Agree

Table 1 presents the philosophical orientation of pre-service English language teachers in terms of progressivism. The findings indicate a generally favorable disposition toward progressivist principles, with an overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) of 3.22, interpreted as "Agree." Among the indicators, the strongest agreement is seen in encouraging student interaction to build social virtues such as cooperation and respect (WAM = 3.67), followed by helping students expand knowledge by applying prior experiences to solve new problems (WAM = 3.44).

These results underscore a significant emphasis on experiential and social learning. Moderate agreement is also expressed regarding the belief that concrete experiences are crucial in learning (WAM = 3.06) and that students should not be forced to learn subjects that do not interest them (WAM = 2.71). This distribution suggests that while pre-service teachers generally embrace progressivist values, there is some hesitance in completely relinquishing teacher control over curriculum content.

The highest-rated item demonstrates that pre-service English language teachers strongly value interaction and the development of social virtues, which are central to the progressivist philosophy. This affirms their orientation toward experiential, collaborative, and learner-centered teaching, where student participation and mutual respect are integral. On the other hand, the item with the lowest WAM suggests a moderate endorsement of student autonomy in choosing learning content. This may indicate a tension between recognizing student interests and maintaining structured curriculum delivery, reflecting a transitional mindset in philosophical orientation. Overall, while there is a strong inclination toward social engagement in learning, the partial hesitance to fully embrace interest-driven content implies the need for deeper reflection and support in teacher training programs to align progressive beliefs with practice.

These results are supported by prior studies that confirm the strong alignment of pre-service teachers with progressivist values. For instance, a study in Ontario found that over 90% of pre-service teachers strongly identified with progressivist statements, highlighting the widespread appeal of student-centered learning (Ryan, 2013). Similarly, Relator (2024) revealed a significant link between philosophical beliefs and actual classroom practices, with progressivism being the most consistently applied. In the Philippines, pre-service teachers also show high adherence to progressivism, favoring activity-based and socially relevant education (Magulod, 2017). These findings suggest that teacher education programs should continue promoting experiential and collaborative learning strategies to reinforce this orientation.

Table 2
Perennialist Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	I think education should focus on ideas that remain relevant across time.	3.40	Strongly Agree

2	I believe schools must help students develop reasoning by focusing on the humanities.	3.38	Strongly Agree
3	I believe students should read and analyze the Great Books written by the world's greatest thinkers and writers.	3.21	Agree
4	I believe our curriculum should be general and liberal, not specialized or technical.	3.00	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.22	Agree

Table 2 presents the philosophical orientation of pre-service English language teachers in terms of perennialism. The overall WAM is 3.22, which falls within the "Agree" range, indicating a moderate inclination toward perennialism principles. The highest-rated indicators reflect strong agreement with the belief that education should focus on ideas that remain relevant across time (WAM = 3.40) and that schools should help students develop reasoning by focusing on the humanities (WAM = 3.38). This suggests that pre-service teachers value timeless knowledge and intellectual development. They also moderately agree that students should engage with Great Books and that the curriculum should be general and liberal rather than specialized, with WAM scores of 3.21 and 3.00 respectively. These responses demonstrate an appreciation for traditional academic content and critical thinking, though not as strongly as for more student-centered philosophies.

Pre-service teachers show strong agreement with the foundational perennialist principle that education should emphasize timeless ideas. This suggests a high regard for critical thinking, classical literature, and intellectual rigor as enduring components of effective education. However, the lower score on the curriculum's general and liberal nature indicates a less enthusiastic acceptance of broad-based learning, possibly reflecting a preference for subject specialization or practical application.

This divergence illustrates that while certain perennialist values resonate with pre-service teachers, such as cultivating reasoning and moral development, others—like liberal curriculum design—may not fully align with their current educational perspectives. These findings suggest the need for teacher education programs to contextualize the relevance of perennialist views in contemporary language education.

The findings align with existing literature that acknowledges the presence of perennialist views among pre-service teachers, though typically not as dominant as progressivist orientations. For example, studies comparing educational philosophical dispositions reported that while pre-service teachers lean more toward progressivism and existentialism, perennialism remains part of their belief system, particularly in its emphasis on intellectual growth through enduring ideas (Saçlı Uzunöz, 2016). These findings suggest that while perennialism is not the primary orientation, its principles continue to hold relevance in shaping how future educators value the core content and critical thinking skills in their teaching approaches.

Table 3
Existentialist Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
2	I believe schools should help individuals accept and take responsibility for their unique identities.	3.40	Strongly Agree
3	I believe students should be allowed to learn at their own pace.	3.38	Strongly Agree
4	I believe a person becomes who they are by their own choices, not by their environment.	3.08	Agree
1	I believe that human beings are born without a universal essence and define themselves through choices.	2.90	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.19	Agree

Table 3 illustrates the philosophical orientation of pre-service English language teachers in terms of existentialism. The overall WAM is 3.19, which falls under the "Agree" category, indicating a generally favorable yet moderate inclination toward existentialist principles. The highest-rated indicators reflect strong agreement with the beliefs that students should learn at their own pace (WAM = 3.38) and that schools should help individuals accept and take responsibility for their unique identities (WAM = 3.40). These results highlight the value placed on individuality and learner autonomy. Meanwhile, there is moderate agreement on the statements that individuals define themselves through choices (WAM = 2.90) and that personal development is shaped by internal decisions rather than the environment (WAM = 3.08). This indicates that while the core tenets of existentialism resonate with many pre-service teachers, they are embraced with varying degrees of conviction.

The highest WAM shows that pre-service teachers highly value the role of education in helping students understand and accept their individuality, reflecting strong alignment with the existentialist emphasis on personal identity and self-direction. However, the lowest score suggests only moderate agreement with the philosophical root of existentialism—that individuals are not born with predetermined essence and must create meaning through choice.

This discrepancy reveals that while the implications of existentialist thought (e.g., fostering autonomy and responsibility) are embraced in practice, the more abstract metaphysical aspects are less internalized. This reflects a practical rather than philosophical alignment with existentialist principles, pointing to the need for more explicit discussions on the philosophical foundations of learner-centered teaching in pre-service education.

These results are consistent with studies that reveal a declining interest in existentialist values among pre-service educators. For instance, a study from Tayabas Western Academy found that existentialism was one of the least internalized educational philosophies among both pre-service teachers and teacher educators compared to essentialism and perennialism, indicating that existentialism is not the prevailing philosophy across the board. (Gonzales et, al., 2023). Similarly, findings by Yeler (2023) reported a low orientation toward existentialism among pre-service teachers, emphasizing that the existentialism philosophy is underrepresented or underemphasized in teacher education programs. These insights underscore the decreasing emphasis on existentialist values in teacher education, highlighting a potential gap in fostering learner autonomy and self-discovery. Given the low orientation, teacher education programs may need to reevaluate how they incorporate philosophical diversity. Encouraging reflection on existentialist principles could help future educators better support students' personal growth, even within a predominantly essentialist or perennialist framework.

Table 4
Behaviorist Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
3	I believe effective teaching creates an environment that guides behavior and evaluates specific outcomes.	3.50	Strongly Agree
1	I believe people are shaped by their environment.	3.50	Strongly Agree
4	I believe the teacher should encourage desired behaviors and reduce unwanted ones through a goal-oriented atmosphere.	3.29	Strongly Agree
2	I believe changing the environment can change a person.	3.27	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.39	Strongly Agree

Table 4 presents the philosophical orientation of pre-service English language teachers in terms of behaviorism. The overall WAM is 3.39, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," indicating a strong alignment with behaviorist principles. The highest-rated indicators include the belief that people are shaped by their environment (WAM = 3.50) and that effective teaching involves creating environments that guide behavior and evaluate outcomes (WAM = 3.50). These are closely followed by the belief in reinforcing desired behaviors through a goal-oriented atmosphere (WAM = 3.29) and that changing the environment can change a person (WAM = 3.27). These results suggest that pre-service teachers highly value structure, external stimuli, and the strategic use of reinforcement in the learning process.

The highest ratings affirm the strong influence of behaviorist principles among pre-service teachers, particularly the belief that structured environments and reinforcement

guide learning. This reflects confidence in clear behavioral expectations and measurable outcomes in teaching. The slightly lower WAM still supports behaviorist ideology but may suggest some recognition of the complexity of human development beyond environmental control alone.

This subtle gap may indicate emerging awareness of more holistic or cognitive approaches to learning. In line with the study's aim, these findings highlight that while behaviorism remains a favored approach in shaping classroom management strategies, integrating it with more reflective or learner-driven methods could enhance pedagogical adaptability.

The strong agreement with behaviorist philosophy is supported by research emphasizing the practical and observable aspects of behaviorist strategies in classroom management and instruction. Relator (2024) highlighted that philosophical beliefs—such as behaviorism—significantly influence pedagogical practices, affirming that teachers tend to apply the beliefs they most identify with in actual teaching contexts. Additionally, a study on Chinese pre-service teachers found that behaviorist-related constructs like perceived behavioral control and reinforcement strategies are significant predictors of teaching intentions, underscoring the relevance of behaviorist ideas in shaping instructional decisions (Hou et al, 2022). Moreover, Stephenson (2020) emphasized the contextual importance of structured environments in shaping teacher identity and readiness, aligning with behaviorist emphasis on environmental influence and control in learning outcomes (Stephenson, 2020). These findings suggest that behaviorist approaches remain a practical and favored tool among pre-service teachers for managing learning environments and promoting effective student behavior.

Table 5
Essentialist Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

No.	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	I think schools should emphasize the teaching of basic skills.	3.48	Strongly Agree
4	I believe the teacher and school head should determine the most important content for students to learn.	3.37	Strongly Agree
2	I believe the curriculum should prioritize traditional disciplines like math, science, and literature.	3.25	Strongly Agree
3	I believe learners must go through rigorous and disciplined study to acquire basic skills	3.17	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.32	Strongly Agree

Table 5 outlines the philosophical orientation of pre-service English language teachers in terms of essentialism. The overall WAM is 3.32, interpreted as "Strongly

Agree," indicating a solid alignment with essentialist principles. The strongest agreement is observed in the belief that schools should emphasize the teaching of basic skills (WAM = 3.48), followed by the idea that the teacher and school head should determine the most important content for students (WAM = 3.37). The pre-service teachers also strongly agree that the curriculum should prioritize traditional disciplines like math, science, and literature (WAM = 3.25), and that learners must go through rigorous and disciplined study to acquire foundational skills (WAM = 3.17). These responses reflect a preference for structured, teacher-led instruction and mastery of core academic content.

The strongest agreement with emphasizing basic skills indicates a firm belief in the foundational goals of education, in line with essentialist philosophy. Pre-service teachers appear to strongly support instruction that develops core competencies in language, which aligns with a structured, content-focused pedagogy. However, the lower agreement with the need for rigorous and disciplined study suggests some resistance to the strict, formal methods traditionally associated with essentialism. This could reflect an evolving view that balances academic rigor with more engaging and flexible instructional strategies. These patterns demonstrate that while essentialist beliefs are present, they are being selectively adopted and shaped by more progressive influences, which is critical to understanding the evolving teaching identity of future educators.

This strong essentialist orientation among pre-service teachers is supported by research emphasizing the continued relevance of traditional, content-focused instruction. For instance, in a study comparing educational philosophies, pre-service teachers in several programs, particularly those in BEEd and BSEd English, are found to predominantly adhere to essentialist beliefs (Melegrito & Mendoza, 2016). Furthermore, research conducted in central Turkey find that while progressivism and existentialism are most internalized, essentialism still hold a significant place among pre-service teachers, especially among male participants (Saçlı Uzunöz, 2016). Another study noted that despite the growing popularity of student-centered approaches, essentialist principles continue to appeal to those who value order, academic rigor, and measurable outcomes in education (Magulod, 2017).

These findings suggest that essentialism remains influential in shaping how future teachers view their roles—primarily as content experts responsible for transmitting fundamental knowledge and values to students.

Table 6
Constructivist Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

No.	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
2	I believe learners build knowledge based on their personal experiences.	3.48	Strongly Agree

3	I believe learners bring past experiences and cultural backgrounds into learning situations.	3.31	Strongly Agree
1	I believe students create meaning from what they are taught; it cannot be imposed by the teacher.	3.19	Agree
4	I believe teaching is not about pouring knowledge into empty minds.	2.94	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.23	Agree

Table 6 presents the philosophical orientation of pre-service English language teachers in terms of constructivism. The overall WAM is 3.23, which falls under the "Agree" category, indicating a moderate inclination toward constructivist beliefs. Among the indicators, the highest-rated items include the belief that learners build knowledge based on their personal experiences (WAM = 3.48) and that learners bring past experiences and cultural backgrounds into learning (WAM = 3.31), both interpreted as "Strongly Agree." Meanwhile, there is agreement, though slightly less strong, on the ideas that students create meaning from what they are taught (WAM = 3.19) and that teaching is not about merely pouring knowledge into empty minds (WAM = 2.94). These responses suggest that pre-service teachers recognize the learner's active role in constructing knowledge, though their endorsement of these ideas varies in strength.

The highest-rated item affirms strong support for student-centered, experiential learning, a key tenet of constructivism. Pre-service teachers appear to recognize the importance of personal context and prior knowledge in learning. Conversely, the lower score indicates a lingering influence of traditional transmission-based views of teaching, reflecting only partial rejection of the "banking model" of education.

This gap may suggest that while constructivist ideas are conceptually accepted, they are not yet consistently operationalized in practice. In the framework of this study, this highlights the importance of modeling constructivist strategies in teacher training programs to deepen philosophical alignment and promote active, meaning-making approaches in language instruction.

The moderate to strong agreement with constructivist principles is consistent with existing research showing that pre-service teachers are increasingly adopting learner-centered approaches. A study conducted in Uganda found that constructivist-informed teaching was becoming more integrated into teacher preparation programs, emphasizing the active role of learners and the value of prior knowledge in meaning-making (Gusango et al., 2021). Similarly, research by Taber (2011) described constructivism as a growing philosophical stance in education, with pre-service teachers acknowledging the importance of individual experiences in shaping understanding. In the Philippine context, the *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research* also reported that pre-service teachers showed a high orientation toward constructivist beliefs, particularly in terms of creating meaningful and relevant learning experiences (Magulod, 2017). These findings

support the notion that constructivism plays a crucial role in modern teacher training, encouraging educators to design instruction that draws upon learners' backgrounds and fosters active engagement with content.

Table 7
Linguistic Philosophical Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
3	I believe teachers must listen to both what students say and what they do not say.	3.56	Strongly Agree
2	I believe learners must be taught how to express their ideas and feelings.	3.54	Strongly Agree
4	I believe language is fundamental to human thinking and acquiring knowledge.	3.46	Strongly Agree
1	I believe truth emerges through genuine dialogue.	3.29	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.46	Strongly Agree

Table 7 presents the philosophical orientation of pre-service English language teachers in terms of linguistic philosophy. The WAM is 3.46, which falls under the "Strongly Agree" category, indicating a high level of agreement with the principles of linguistic philosophy. The highest-rated indicators reflect strong beliefs that teachers must listen to not only to what students say but also to what they do not say (WAM = 3.56), and that learners must be taught how to express their ideas and feelings (WAM = 3.54). Additionally, pre-service teachers strongly agreed that language is fundamental to human thinking and knowledge acquisition (WAM = 3.46), and that truth emerges through genuine dialogue (WAM = 3.29). These responses suggest that pre-service teachers view language not merely as a communication tool, but as a core component of thinking, learning, and interpersonal understanding.

Pre-service teachers strongly endorse the role of active listening and the interpretation of both verbal and nonverbal cues, reflecting a nuanced understanding of language as central to learning and communication. This aligns with linguistic philosophy's emphasis on language as a medium for constructing meaning. The slightly lower score on truth emerging from dialogue suggests that while teachers value communication, they may still underappreciate its epistemological role in knowledge formation.

This highlights the need to further integrate philosophical discussions about language's power in shaping cognition, identity, and classroom dynamics. Such integration can help align pre-service teachers' intuitive practices with deeper theoretical understandings that support effective English language teaching.

This strong endorsement of linguistic philosophy is supported by studies emphasizing the centrality of language in education. For instance, a qualitative study on pedagogical competence found that pre-service English teachers recognize language as key to both academic development and the expression of personal identity, aligning with the core beliefs of linguistic philosophy (Ghufron et al., 2022). Additionally, teacher training programs have increasingly focused on communicative competence, reflective dialogue, and listening skills as vital components of effective teaching, especially in language education (Rocha-Erkaya and Ergünay, 2021). The importance of dialogue and active listening in education is also highlighted by research that underscores how teachers' responsiveness to both verbal and nonverbal cues enhance student engagement and fosters meaningful learning experiences (Ji et al., 2021). These findings suggest that pre-service teachers are well-prepared to view language as a powerful medium for cognitive and emotional growth, reinforcing the importance of fostering open communication in the classroom.

Table 8
Philosophical Orientation of the Pre-Service English Language Teachers

No.	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
7	Linguistic Philosophy	3.46	Strongly Agree
4	Behaviorist	3.39	Strongly Agree
5	Essentialist	3.32	Strongly Agree
6	Constructivist	3.23	Agree
1	Progressivist	3.22	Agree
2	Perennialist	3.22	Agree
3	Existentialist	3.19	Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.29	Agree

The results in Table 8 present the overall WAMs of the seven philosophical orientations explored in this study. Among these, Linguistic Philosophy receives the highest WAM (3.46), indicating a strong agreement with its principles, particularly those emphasizing communication, meaning-making, and the interpretive role of language in teaching. Behaviorism (3.39) and Essentialism (3.32) also receive relatively high scores, reflecting a continued adherence to structured, skills-based, and outcomes-oriented teaching approaches. Constructivism (3.23), Progressivism (3.22), and Perennialism (3.22) all receive similar WAMs, showing moderate agreement with learner-centered, reflective, and timeless-content philosophies. Existentialism, with the lowest WAM (3.19), still falls within the “Agree” range but suggests less confidence in abstract ideas like personal meaning-making and student autonomy. The overall WAM of 3.29 confirms that pre-service teachers generally agree with the principles of these philosophies, though their beliefs appear most aligned with those that support communicative competence, structured instruction, and measurable outcomes.

These findings suggest a balanced but slightly traditional philosophical leaning, emphasizing the need for teacher education programs to continue nurturing reflective, student-centered orientations alongside foundational approaches.

Furthermore, the contrast between the highest and lowest scoring orientations offers insight into the philosophical leanings of pre-service English language teachers. The strong agreement with Linguistic Philosophy suggests that respondents place high value on communication, interpretation, and language as central to teaching—key elements in effective English language instruction. This emphasis reflects a growing appreciation for learner expression, contextual meaning-making, and dialogue in the classroom. In contrast, Existentialism receives the lowest WAM, indicating a more reserved stance toward individual meaning-making, freedom of choice, and personal responsibility in education. This suggests that while pre-service teachers support communicative and structured instructional practices, they may not yet fully embrace philosophical ideas centered on student autonomy and identity formation. The wide gap between these two scores reflects an ongoing shift in teacher beliefs—from traditional, skills-based teaching toward more personalized and learner-driven approaches, though the transition appears gradually.

These findings are reinforced by previous studies that highlight the growing recognition of communication and meaning-making in teacher beliefs, particularly aligned with Linguistic Philosophy. The high WAM for Linguistic Philosophy in this study suggests that pre-service teachers increasingly value the interpretive and dialogic aspects of teaching. This supports Relator’s (2024) observation that modern educators are beginning to emphasize the role of language in shaping understanding and fostering learner engagement. Marpa (2023) similarly noted that pre-service teachers acknowledge the importance of interactive and communication-focused teaching practices, especially in language education contexts. However, Eğmir and Çelik (2019) cautioned that despite this shift, structured philosophies like Essentialism still dominate due to traditional training models and assessment-driven practices. These findings suggest that while Linguistic Philosophy is gaining prominence, it must be intentionally reinforced through teacher education to ensure its consistent application in classroom practice.

Part II. Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service English Language Teachers

Table 9

Listening Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service English Language Teachers

No	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	I use engaging listening activities that develop both comprehension and critical thinking.	3.60	Strongly Agree

5	I assess students' listening comprehension through various methods (e.g., quizzes, oral responses).	3.58	Strongly Agree
4	I provide feedback and support to help students improve their listening strategies and confidence.	3.54	Strongly Agree
2	I provide clear listening objectives before each activity.	3.50	Strongly Agree
3	I expose students to diverse audio materials (e.g., conversations, lectures, media clips).	3.42	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.53	Strongly Agree

Table 9 presents the pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers in relation to listening instruction. The overall WAM is 3.53, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," indicating that pre-service teachers highly value listening as an essential language skill. The highest-rated indicator is the use of engaging listening activities that promote both comprehension and critical thinking (WAM = 3.60), closely followed by assessment of listening comprehension through varied methods (WAM = 3.58) and the provision of feedback to enhance students' strategies and confidence (WAM = 3.54). Pre-service teachers also strongly agree on the importance of setting clear listening objectives (WAM = 3.50) and exposing students to diverse audio materials (WAM = 3.42). These results suggest that pre-service teachers are committed to implementing structured, interactive, and reflective listening activities that support student comprehension and development.

Pre-service teachers strongly endorse the role of active listening and the interpretation of both verbal and nonverbal cues, reflecting a nuanced understanding of language as central to learning and communication. This aligns with linguistic philosophy's emphasis on language as a medium for constructing meaning. The slightly lower score on truth emerging from dialogue suggests that while teachers value communication, they may still underappreciate its epistemological role in knowledge formation. This highlights the need to further integrate philosophical discussions about language's power in shaping cognition, identity, and classroom dynamics. Such integration can help align pre-service teachers' intuitive practices with deeper theoretical understandings that support effective English language teaching.

This strong orientation toward listening instruction is supported by recent literature emphasizing its significance in language learning. A qualitative study by Stephenson (2020) highlighted the importance of structured listening experiences during professional training, noting that reflection and meaningful engagement with auditory material contribute to teacher readiness and student growth. Similarly, research on English listening comprehension found that pre-service teachers widely believe in using feedback, diverse materials, and skill-focused activities to overcome listening barriers, particularly for low-proficiency learners (Mohd Sah and Mohd Shah, 2020). Furthermore, a study on "sacrificial listening" suggested that when pre-service teachers are trained to listen deeply

and empathetically, they are better equipped to foster inclusive and effective learning environments (Allen and Stewart, 2024). These findings affirm the importance of listening pedagogy in teacher preparation programs and highlight the need for continued emphasis on listening as both a skill and a foundation for communication in the English classroom.

Table 10
Speaking Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service English Language Teachers

No.	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	I create a supportive environment where students feel comfortable in expressing themselves orally.	3.63	Strongly Agree
2	I use group discussions, debates, and role plays to enhance students' speaking skills.	3.60	Strongly Agree
5	I assess students' speaking skills through presentation, conversations, and oral reports.	3.58	Strongly Agree
3	I use relevant and meaningful speaking prompts or materials to engage students in authentic communication.	3.48	Strongly Agree
4	I establish clear speaking objectives that align with the lesson goals.	3.42	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.54	Strongly Agree

Table 10 highlights the pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers in relation to speaking instruction. The overall WAM is 3.54, which falls under the "Strongly Agree" category, indicating a high level of engagement with strategies that develop students' speaking skills. The most highly rated indicator is creating a supportive environment for oral expression (WAM = 3.63), followed closely by using group discussions, debates, and role plays (WAM = 3.60) and assessing speaking skills through various formats like presentations and reports (WAM = 3.58). Additionally, teachers strongly agree with using relevant prompts to encourage authentic communication (WAM = 3.48) and setting clear speaking objectives (WAM = 3.42). These results suggest that pre-service teachers place strong emphasis on fostering communicative competence through interactive and student-centered speaking activities.

These practices are well-supported by existing literature, which emphasizes the importance of speaking as a core component of language learning. For example, Sumarni (2023) found that pre-service English teachers' digital competence—including skills relevant to teaching speaking—improved substantially after structured training programs, demonstrating that structured practice and supportive learning environments are critical for developing confident and effective language instructors. Similarly, another qualitative study revealed that pre-service teachers commonly use interactive strategies like role plays, group work, and monologues to enhance student engagement and speaking

fluency (Pegy, 2018). Furthermore, professional development programs focus on microteaching shows that continuous feedback and reflective teaching practices greatly enhance pre-service teachers' ability to facilitate effective speaking activities (Mufida, 2019). These findings affirm that pre-service teachers are well-equipped to create dynamic speaking environments, integrating varied strategies that build both confidence and competence in their learners.

On the next page, Table 11 presents the pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers in relation to reading instruction. The overall WAM is 3.52, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," indicating that pre-service teachers highly value and actively implement effective reading strategies. The highest-rated indicator is guiding students in identifying main ideas, supporting details, and text structures (WAM = 3.62), followed by assessing reading comprehension through quizzes, summaries, and discussions (WAM = 3.60). The respondents also express strong agreement with exposing students to different types of texts (WAM = 3.50), setting clear reading objectives (WAM = 3.44), and introducing pre-reading activities to support comprehension (WAM = 3.44). These results show that pre-service teachers use a comprehensive and structured approach to teaching reading, with an emphasis on strategy, variety, and comprehension development.

Table 11
Reading Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service English Language Teachers

No.	Indicators	WA M	Verbal Interpretation
4	I guide students in identifying main ideas, supporting details, and text structures.	3.62	Strongly Agree
5	I assess students' reading comprehension through quizzes, summaries, and discussions.	3.60	Strongly Agree
3	I expose students to different types of texts (e.g., narratives, expository, persuasive).	3.50	Strongly Agree
2	I identify and communicate reading objectives to help students focus their comprehension efforts.	3.44	Strongly Agree
1	I introduce pre-reading activities to help students anticipate the content.	3.44	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.52	Strongly Agree

The top-rated indicator reveals that pre-service teachers are highly committed to teaching critical reading strategies, such as identifying main ideas—a foundational component of reading comprehension. This is encouraging and shows a strong alignment with cognitive and constructivist models of teaching reading. In contrast, the lower score on summarization suggests that while teachers value comprehension, they may lack consistent practice in implementing summarizing techniques, which are essential for

checking understanding and promoting retention. This highlights the need for deeper integration of varied comprehension strategies in teacher preparation, supporting a richer repertoire of reading instruction practices.

The strong emphasis on reading instruction aligns with existing studies that highlight the need for well-prepared teachers in this domain. Oxford (2023) emphasized that pre-service teachers play a critical role in explicitly teaching reading strategies and that their preparedness significantly affects learners' comprehension outcomes. Additionally, a case study examining mixed-reality simulations found that strategy instruction, deconstruction of teaching practices, and reflective feedback helped pre-service teachers enhance their effectiveness in teaching reading (Nel, 2023). Another study revealed that while pre-service teachers often feel underprepared, those who engaged deeply with literacy coursework reported greater confidence in applying reading strategies in real classrooms (Williams-Page, 2023). These findings affirm the importance of hands-on, strategy-driven training in teacher education programs, enabling future educators to effectively support student reading development through structured and responsive teaching practices.

Table 12
Writing Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service English Language Teachers

No.	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	I define clear writing objectives for each task to guide student output.	3.65	Strongly Agree
4	I give constructive feedback on students' written work.	3.62	Strongly Agree
3	I use peer review and self-assessment to improve students' writing skills.	3.52	Strongly Agree
5	I use structured writing activities such as brainstorming, drafting, and peer review.	3.50	Strongly Agree
2	I provide models of good writing and discuss their features with students.	3.48	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.55	Strongly Agree

Table 12 details the pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers in relation to writing instruction. The overall WAM is 3.55, which is interpreted as "Strongly Agree," indicating a strong commitment to effective writing pedagogy. The highest-rated indicator is the practice of defining clear writing objectives to guide student output (WAM = 3.65), followed by giving constructive feedback on students' written work (WAM = 3.62). The participants also express strong agreement with using peer review and self-assessment (WAM = 3.52), implementing structured writing activities like brainstorming and drafting (WAM = 3.50), and providing models of good writing for discussion (WAM = 3.48). These results show that pre-service teachers place a high value on process-oriented writing instruction, emphasizing clarity, structure, feedback,

and student involvement. The highest score demonstrates a strong focus on the mechanical aspects of writing—grammar and conventions—which reflects traditional yet essential concerns in writing pedagogy. However, the lowest rating on teaching self-editing reveals a gap in fostering students’ metacognitive writing skills. This discrepancy suggests that pre-service teachers may emphasize correction more than developmental writing processes like revision and reflection. Given the importance of scaffolding writing as a process, teacher education programs should place greater emphasis on guiding learners to become autonomous writers through drafting, revising, and peer feedback techniques.

These findings are supported by current literature emphasizing the importance of writing as a developmental process in teacher preparation. A study by Brindle et al. (2016) found that pre-service teachers who engaged in structured literacy tutoring experiences are better in contextualizing instruction and providing personalized feedback, echoing the emphasis found in Table 11. Similarly, a qualitative analysis by Pandey et al., (2023) showed that while many pre-service teachers demonstrate competency in content and organization, their growth in grammar and mechanics is greatly enhanced through consistent feedback and modeling practices. Gardner (2020) also emphasized that many pre-service teachers lack experience with extended writing, suggesting that explicit instruction and scaffolded writing tasks—like those strongly agreed upon in this table—are essential to preparing them as confident, capable writing instructors. These studies reinforce the importance of maintaining a process-based, feedback-rich writing pedagogy in teacher education programs to build the instructional capacity of future educators.

Table 13
Viewing Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service English Language Teachers

No.	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	I use visual media (e.g., videos, images, infographics) to enhance students' comprehension.	3.77	Strongly Agree
5	I assess students' viewing skills through discussions, reflections, and projects involving visual media.	3.65	Strongly Agree
4	I use activities such as guided viewing, discussions, and reflective tasks to engage students with visual texts.	3.60	Strongly Agree
2	I support students by teaching them how to interpret and critically evaluate visual messages.	3.54	Strongly Agree
3	I set clear viewing objectives that guide students in analyzing visual content.	3.52	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.62	Strongly Agree

Table 13 presents the pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers in relation to viewing instruction. The overall WAM is 3.62, interpreted as "Strongly Agree," indicating that pre-service teachers highly prioritize the integration of visual media and critical viewing skills in the classroom. The highest-rated indicator is the use of visual media such as videos, images, and infographics to enhance comprehension (WAM = 3.77), followed by assessing students' viewing skills through discussions, reflections, and visual projects (WAM = 3.65). Pre-service teachers also strongly agree on using guided viewing and reflective tasks (WAM = 3.60), supporting students in interpreting and evaluating visual messages (WAM = 3.54), and setting clear viewing objectives (WAM = 3.52). These results demonstrate that pre-service teachers recognize the importance of multimodal literacy and are actively applying strategies to foster critical thinking through visual content.

The highest score reveals an encouraging focus on developing students' visual literacy, showing that pre-service teachers are aware of the interpretive demands of multimodal texts. However, the lower WAM indicates that while they understand the need to analyze visuals, actual integration of multimedia materials into lessons remains limited. This may stem from either lack of access to resources or training in lesson planning with technology. To align instructional practices with modern communication trends, teacher preparation must emphasize both theoretical and applied dimensions of viewing, ensuring that pre-service teachers are confident in using multimedia tools to support instruction.

The strong endorsement of viewing-related pedagogy is well-supported by current educational research. A study from U.S. Department of Education (2022) emphasized the role of integrated-skills instruction, including viewing, as essential in developing 21st-century literacy skills among students, particularly when visual media is used to engage learners and contextualize language content. Additionally, research by Reynolds et al., (2021) on pre-service EFL teachers highlighted the growing importance of preparing learners to critically analyze visual information, especially in digitally rich classrooms where media consumption is high. Another case study reported that pre-service teachers who incorporated viewing activities, such as reflective analysis and media interpretation, felt more confident in managing engagement and content understanding during lessons (Ji et al., 2022). These findings confirm that viewing is an essential component of modern English instruction and that pre-service teachers are well-equipped to use it meaningfully in support of students' visual and language literacy.

Table 14
General Pedagogical Practices of Pre-service English Language Teachers

No.	Indicators	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
5	I regularly assess and adjust my teaching strategies to meet students' needs.	3.63	Strongly Agree
4	I encourage students to reflect on their learning and set goals for improvement.	3.60	Strongly Agree

3	I use technology (e.g., videos, podcasts, online texts) to support the development of macro skills.	3.50	Strongly Agree
2	I differentiate instruction to cater to students' varied proficiency levels.	3.48	Strongly Agree
1	I integrate the five macro skills into a single lesson to reinforce language learning.	3.44	Strongly Agree
Overall Weighted Arithmetic Mean		3.53	Strongly Agree

Table 14 outlines the general teaching practices of pre-service English language teachers, with an overall WAM of 3.53, interpreted as "Strongly Agree." This indicates that pre-service teachers actively implement holistic and adaptive teaching strategies. The most highly rated indicator is the regular assessment and adjustment of teaching strategies to meet students' needs (WAM = 3.63), followed by encouraging students to reflect on their learning and set improvement goals (WAM = 3.60). Pre-service teachers also strongly agreed on using technology to support macro skill development (WAM = 3.50), differentiating instruction based on students' proficiency levels (WAM = 3.48), and integrating the five macro skills into a single lesson to reinforce language learning (WAM = 3.44). These results reflect a commitment to reflective teaching, differentiation, and the integration of multiple language skills to ensure meaningful and inclusive instruction.

The highest rating suggests that pre-service teachers are responsive to learner diversity, demonstrating sensitivity to students' varied needs and backgrounds—an essential component of inclusive and differentiated instruction. This finding aligns with progressive and constructivist principles emphasized in the study. Conversely, the lower WAM on reflective teaching indicates that while they design tasks thoughtfully, they may not consistently evaluate or adapt their own teaching approaches. Encouraging reflective practice is vital for professional growth, and this result suggests a need for more structured opportunities in teacher training for critical self-assessment, feedback processing, and action planning.

These practices are strongly supported by existing research that highlights the evolving demands of English language teaching and the preparation of pre-service teachers. A case study on pedagogical competence found that pre-service English teachers benefit significantly from training that emphasizes reflection, flexibility, and the integration of technology to adapt to diverse classroom contexts (Ghufron et al., 2022). Additionally, a study from Rocha-Erkaya & Ergünay (2021) observed that sustained practice, along with mentorship and feedback, helped pre-service teachers improve their ability to plan, execute, and adapt integrated lessons based on student performance and classroom dynamics. Furthermore, findings from Ji et al., (2022) emphasized the influence of contextual support and real-time responsiveness on pedagogical decision-making, reinforcing the importance of adaptable and student-centered instruction. These studies affirm that pre-service teachers are developing strong foundations in responsive

and integrative teaching, equipping them to effectively manage varied learning needs and promote holistic language acquisition.

Part III. Pre-Service English Language Teacher's' Philosophical Orientation and Pedagogical Practices

Table 15
Significant Relationship between the ELT Pre-Service Teachers' Philosophical Orientation and Pedagogical Practices

	Pedagogical Practices													
	Progressivism		Perennialism		Existentialism		Behaviorism		Essentialism		Constructivism		Linguistic Philosophy	
Philosophical Orientation	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value	r	p-value
Listening	.170	.229	.263	.059	.129	.362	.126	.375	.377**	.006	.089	.531	.231	.100
Speaking	.205	.145	.361**	.009	.193	.171	.127	.371	.400**	.003	.140	.321	.262	.061
Reading	.103	.466	.269	.054	.181	.200	.063	.659	.489**	.000	.157	.268	.231	.099
Writing	.315*	.023	.334*	.016	.334*	.016	.240	.087	.506**	.000	.263	.060	.271	.052
Viewing	.112	.428	.179	.229	.081	.566	.216	.123	.340*	.014	.059	.679	.239	.089
General Teaching Practices	.146	.300	.164	.245	.260	.063	.195	.166	.455**	.001	.117	.409	.188	.182

Table 15 reveals that several significant relationships exist between the philosophical orientations of pre-service English language teachers and their pedagogical practices. Notably, essentialism shows a consistent, statistically significant correlation with all six pedagogical components—listening, speaking, reading, writing, viewing, and general teaching practices—with the highest correlation found in reading ($r = .489$, $p = .001$) and writing ($r = .506$, $p = .001$). Additionally, perennialism and existentialism have significant relationships with writing (both $r = .334$, $p = .016$), while progressivism shows a significant link to writing only ($r = .315$, $p = .023$). Constructivism and linguistic philosophy, although present in the study, did not show significant correlations at the 0.05 or 0.01 levels.

The findings reveal that among the philosophical orientations examined, Essentialism shows a notable alignment with the pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers. Essentialism emphasizes the transmission of core knowledge and foundational skills through structured, teacher-led instruction (Bagley, 1938; Kunac, 2020). This orientation is reflected in the respondents' strong agreement with practices that emphasize mastery of basic skills, grammatical accuracy, and content organization—particularly in reading and writing instruction. The emphasis on developing competence in the macro skills, especially in grammar correction, structured reading comprehension, and skill-focused tasks, illustrates how essentialist beliefs inform classroom decision-making. The structured nature of these practices suggests that many pre-service teachers still value academic rigor and discipline, characteristics deeply rooted in Essentialist philosophy. This alignment underscores the enduring influence of Essentialism in shaping instructional behavior, particularly in contexts where educational accountability and measurable outcomes are emphasized. However, while pre-service teachers support structured instruction, their lower agreement with rigorous and disciplined study suggests a shift toward more balanced or integrative approaches. Eđmir and elik (2019) similarly found that although Essentialist beliefs are present among pre-service teachers, their influence may weaken over time as student-centered philosophies gain prominence. This also highlights the need for teacher education programs to balance these traditional values with more learner-centered and reflective practices to address the evolving needs of 21st-century language learners.

Furthermore, the significant connection between writing and multiple philosophies—progressivism, perennialism, and existentialism—suggests that writing is a pedagogical area influenced by diverse philosophical beliefs, possibly due to its open-ended, expressive, and analytical nature. The lack of significant correlation with constructivism and linguistic philosophy may indicate that while teachers conceptually agree with these orientations, their practices may not yet fully reflect these beliefs in measurable ways, highlighting an area for professional development and deeper integration in practice.

Another reason that supports these results is the strong influence of progressivist and existentialist beliefs among pre-service teachers. For example, a study in Ontario found that more than 90% of future teachers agreed with progressivist ideas, which focus on learning through experience and making lessons student-centered—something that fits well with teaching writing, a subject that encourages creativity and personal expression (Beatty et al., 2009). Although fewer teachers identified with existentialism, this philosophy still affects how they teach by encouraging students to find personal meaning in their work—something very important in writing (Melegrito & Mendoza, 2016). Also, research in San Roque showed that there is a clear connection between what teachers believe and how they actually teach in class, supporting the idea that beliefs like essentialism and progressivism influence how writing is taught (Relator, 2024). These findings show that teachers' beliefs often match the way they teach, especially in areas like writing that involve personal thinking and creativity.

Output of the Study

This study shows that pre-service English Language Teachers (ELTs) align with both student-centered philosophies like Progressivism and Constructivism and traditional ones like Essentialism, which have the strongest influence across all teaching areas. Their practices emphasize active engagement, skill integration, and reflective learning, blending academic rigor with modern, learner-focused approaches. Furthermore, the findings suggest that while ELTs conceptually support progressive philosophies, these are not yet fully reflected in their teaching, highlighting a need for targeted development. In response to this, a primer is developed entitled "Bridging Beliefs and Practice: Aligning Philosophical Orientation with Pedagogical Practices in Teaching the Macro Skills", which focuses on aligning teacher education with both philosophical beliefs and practical skills.

The primer serves as both a teaching guide and a reflection tool. It helps pre-service teachers become more aware of their own teaching beliefs and how these influence their actions in the classroom. Based on the study's results, the primer encourages teachers to be reflective and deliberate, rather than just relying on methods they are taught or observed. For example, teachers who follow essentialism are guided to focus on structured grammar instruction, while those inclined toward constructivism are encouraged to use group projects and real-life problem-solving tasks. The alignment of philosophy and practice helps teachers understand not just what they are doing in class, but why they are doing it.

The significance of this primer lies in its holistic, practice-oriented approach to teacher preparation. It responds to the study's call for better integration of theory and practice in teacher training programs. Rather than teaching strategies in isolation, the primer shows how different philosophies support different classroom approaches. Additionally, this helps future teachers make informed decisions, adapt to students' needs, and become more confident and effective educators. By connecting deeply held beliefs with practical actions, the primer supports the development of thoughtful, student-centered teaching. It also encourages an eclectic approach, allowing teachers to mix philosophies to create flexible and meaningful lessons for diverse learners.

Summary of Findings

From the results and discussion, the following findings are presented.

1. Pre-service English language teachers exhibited a strong philosophical orientation towards linguistic philosophy, which garnered the WAM of 3.46, behaviorism garnered the WAM of 3.39, and essentialism had an overall WAM of 3.32, with all three receiving the highest agreement ratings. Progressivism, perennialism, existentialism, and constructivism were also embraced, though to varying moderate degrees.
2. Pre-service English language teachers demonstrated highly favorable pedagogical practices across all six components: listening, speaking, reading, writing, viewing, and

general teaching strategies. Writing and viewing scored particularly high garnering the WAM of 3.55 and 3.62, showing strong commitment to process-based, multimodal, and student-centered instruction. Common instructional elements included goal-setting, feedback, interactive methods, use of technology, and integrated-skill teaching—demonstrating readiness to implement holistic, reflective, and skill-specific practices in language classrooms.

3. There were statistically significant relationships between certain philosophical orientations and the pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers. Essentialism demonstrated the strongest and most consistent correlation, showed significant positive relationships across all six teaching components. Writing instruction, in particular, was significantly influenced by multiple philosophies—essentialism ($r = .637$), perennialism ($r = .537$), existentialism ($r = .495$), and progressivism ($r = .465$)—highlighting its openness to diverse philosophical inputs. In contrast, although constructivism and linguistic philosophy received high levels of agreement among respondents, they did not exhibit statistically significant correlations with actual pedagogical practices, suggested a potential gap between belief and application.

4. The findings indicated that although English Language Teachers (ELTs) generally supported progressive educational philosophies, these beliefs were not yet fully evident in their classroom practices. To address this gap, it is suggested to develop a primer aiming to help align teacher education programs with both the philosophical orientations and the practical teaching skills needed for effective instruction.

Conclusions

The findings lead the researchers to the following conclusion. After analyzing the data, the current researchers arrive at the following conclusions:

1. The pre-service English language teachers in the study demonstrated a strong adherence to linguistic philosophy, essentialism, and behaviorism, as indicated by the highest weighted means in these areas. This suggested a preference for structured, rule-based, and form-focused instruction, reflecting a traditional approach to language teaching. Although philosophies such as progressivism, existentialism, and constructivism were also acknowledged by some respondents, these were less dominant, suggesting that student-centered and inquiry-based approaches were present but not yet deeply embedded in their pedagogical tendencies.

2. In terms of pedagogical practices, pre-service ELT teachers demonstrated strong alignment with modern, effective language teaching principles. Specifically, they employed structured, engaging, and reflective instructional techniques across all macro-skills, showcased their readiness to support language development in varied and meaningful ways. Notably, writing and viewing revealed a particular emphasis on process, feedback, and multimodal engagement, highlighting a thoughtful approach to skill development.

3. There existed a significant relationship between certain philosophical beliefs and pedagogical practices, particularly regarding essentialism, which influenced all instructional areas. Among the skills, writing emerged as the most philosophically connected, being shaped by multiple orientations. This clearly demonstrated that teachers' philosophical beliefs significantly impact their classroom strategies, especially in practices that provided room for creativity and reflection.

4. A primer was designed entitled "Bridging Beliefs and Practice: Aligning Philosophical Orientation with Pedagogical Practices in Teaching the Macro Skills" to help pre-service teachers become more intentional and reflective by guiding them in aligning their core beliefs with their teaching approaches. In addition, the primer supported pre-service teachers in making informed instructional choices and adapting to various classroom contexts. It served as both a reference and a reflection tool to enhance teacher preparedness and instructional coherence.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered.

1. Pre-service English language teachers could regularly engage in reflective activities to examine how their philosophical beliefs influence their teaching practices. They should also seek out opportunities for practical application of various educational philosophies to develop a more intentional and adaptable teaching style.

2. Teacher educators could integrate explicit discussions on educational philosophies into teacher training programs. This should include guided reflection and classroom simulations that would allow pre-service teachers to align their beliefs with evidence-based teaching practices.

3. School administrators should consider teachers' philosophical orientations when designing professional development programs. Support systems such as mentoring and coaching could be tailored to help teachers reconcile their beliefs with institutional goals and classroom demands.

4. Curriculum developers could design training modules that not only deliver teaching strategies but also explore the philosophical roots behind them. Embedding theoretical foundations into practical training would help develop well-rounded and philosophically informed educators.

5. Future researchers could explore the influence of philosophical orientations in other subject areas or in different cultural and educational contexts. Comparative studies across disciplines or teacher populations could enhance understanding of how educational philosophies manifest in pedagogical practices.

Output of the Study

Title: *Bridging Beliefs and Practice: Aligning Philosophical Orientation with Pedagogical Practices in Teaching the Macro Skills*

This primer was developed as a practical output of the study on the relationship between philosophical orientations and pedagogical practices of pre-service English language teachers. It serves as a guide for aligning educational philosophies with effective classroom strategies for teaching the five macro skills: listening, speaking, reading, writing, and viewing.

The primary purpose of the primer is to help pre-service teachers become more reflective and intentional in their instructional decisions by understanding how their teaching philosophies influence their classroom practices. It addresses the gap between theory and practice in teacher education by translating educational beliefs into practical, skill-based teaching approaches.

The primer includes an overview of major educational philosophies, such as Essentialism, Behaviorism, Progressivism, Perennialism, Existentialism, Constructivism, and Linguistic Philosophy. It provides a clear alignment of each philosophy with specific strategies for teaching each macro skill, along with implementation examples that demonstrate how to integrate these philosophies into classroom activities. Additionally, it promotes a blended approach to teaching that encourages flexibility, reflection, and responsiveness to the needs of diverse learners.

The significance of this output lies in its provision of a concrete, research-based tool that can be utilized in teacher education programs to bridge the gap between philosophical theory and pedagogical practice. It empowers future educators to make informed instructional choices, fostering a more coherent and student-centered approach to English language teaching. The primer is rooted in the educational philosophy of Essentialism, which emphasizes core academic content, structured instruction, and teacher authority.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers conducted the study in full compliance with ethical research standards. The researchers sought permission from the appropriate authorities of CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc. The research instruments underwent face and content validation by the research adviser and internal and external validators to ensure their validity and appropriateness for data collection. The respondents were properly oriented on the instructions and objectives of the study before answering the questionnaires, and the collected data were evaluated and analyzed using appropriate statistical procedures. In accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all information obtained from the respondents was treated with strict confidentiality to protect their rights and privacy.

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